

Supplementary Material

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A Problem Specific Prompts used

This appendix provides the exact problem specification prompts used to initialize the AAD process in our experiments. Including these prompts verbatim is essential for reproducibility, as they define the optimization task, interface constraints and permissible implementation details exposed to the LLM.

Appendix A.1 documents the prompt used for the SBOX-COST benchmark in Experiment 1, while Appendix A.2 reports the corresponding prompt for the MA-BBOB benchmark used in Experiment 2.

All AAD methods compared in this paper (LLaMEA, LLaMEA-SAGE, LHNS, and MCTS-AHD) were initialized using the same problem specification prompts for a given benchmark. Differences in performance therefore arise from the search strategies and mutation mechanisms rather than differences in task formulation.

A.1 SBOX

Problem specification prompt

```
You are an excellent Python programmer.
You are a Python expert working on a new optimization algorithm.
You can use numpy v2 and some other standard libraries.
Your task is to develop a novel heuristic optimization algorithm for continuous optimization problems.
The optimization algorithm should work on different instances of noiseless unconstrained functions.
Your task is to write the optimization algorithm in Python code.
Each of the optimization functions has a search space between -5.0 (lower bound) and 5.0 (upper bound).
The dimensionality can be varied.
The code should contain an '__init__(self, budget, dim)' function with optional additional arguments
and the function 'def __call__(self, func)',
which should optimize the black box function 'func' using 'self.budget' function evaluations.
The func() can only be called as many times as the budget allows, not more.

An example of such code (a simple random search), is as follows:
'''python
import numpy as np
import math

class RandomSearch:
    def __init__(self, budget=10000, dim=10):
        self.budget = budget
        self.dim = dim
    def __call__(self, func):
        self.f_opt = np.inf
        self.x_opt = None
        for i in range(self.budget):
            x = np.random.uniform(func.bounds.lb, func.bounds.ub)

            f = func(x)
            if f < self.f_opt:
                self.f_opt = f
                self.x_opt = x

        return self.f_opt, self.x_opt
'''

Give an excellent and novel heuristic algorithm to solve this task and also give it a one-line description,
describing the main idea. Give the response in the format:
# Description: <short-description>
# Code:
```

```

'''python
<code>
'''

```

A.2 MA-BBOB

Problem specification prompt

```

You are an excellent Python programmer.
You are a Python developer working on a new optimization algorithm.
Your task is to develop a novel heuristic optimization algorithm for continuous optimization problems.
The optimization algorithm should handle a wide range of noiseless functions.
Your task is to write the optimization algorithm in Python code.
Each of the optimization functions has a search space between -5.0 (lower bound) and 5.0 (upper bound).
The dimensionality can be varied.
The code should contain an '__init__(self, budget, dim)' function with optional additional arguments
and the function 'def __call__(self, func)', which should optimize the black box function 'func'
using 'self.budget' function evaluations.
The func() can only be called as many times as the budget allows, not more.

An example of such code (a simple random search), is as follows:
'''python
import numpy as np

class RandomSearch:
    def __init__(self, budget=10000, dim=10):
        self.budget = budget
        self.dim = dim

    def __call__(self, func):
        self.f_opt = np.inf
        self.x_opt = None
        for i in range(self.budget):
            x = np.random.uniform(func.bounds.lb, func.bounds.ub)

            f = func(x)
            if f < self.f_opt:
                self.f_opt = f
                self.x_opt = x

        return self.f_opt, self.x_opt
'''

Give an excellent and novel heuristic algorithm to solve this task and also give it a one-line description,
describing the main idea. Give the response in the format:
# Description: <short-description>
# Code:
'''python
<code>
'''
", "cost": 0.0001131, "tokens": 0}

```

B Token Costs per Method

As the usage of LLMs can be expensive, either in compute or in API costs, we compare the number of LLM tokens required to do a full AAD run per method. In Figure 1, the average total number of tokens per run is shown. We can observe that LHNS is the most token efficient method, this is most likely not because of greater efficiency of the approach, but because it tends to generate less complex code, which consumes fewer tokens. LLaMEA and LLaMEA-SAGE are very close to each other, with the additional code feature guidance increasing the token cost only marginally. This shows that LLaMEA-SAGE *preserves scalability* relative to vanilla LLaMEA. MCTS-AHD has by far the highest token cost (more than twice as high as LLaMEA) as it queries the LLM several times per solution, while the other methods only query the LLM once per generated algorithm.

Fig. 1. Average number of LLM tokens used per AAD method for one run of generating 200 algorithms.

C LLM Ablation studies

This appendix reports an additional ablation experiment assessing the robustness of the proposed code feature guided mutation mechanism on a different LLM backend. While the main paper focuses on results obtained using the GPT-5-mini model, we repeat experiment 2 using the Gemini-2.0-flash-lite model to evaluate whether the observed performance trends are model-specific.

Figure 2 compares the anytime performance (AOCC) of LLaMEA-SAGE and baseline methods on the MA-BBOB benchmark under both LLM backends. Although absolute performance levels differ, the relative advantage of code feature guided mutation remains consistent.

These results support the claim that the proposed guidance mechanism captures structural signals that generalize across LLM implementations, rather than exploiting idiosyncrasies of a single model.

Fig. 2. Average best-so-far fitness (AOCC) over time of the SOTA baselines and the proposed code feature guided approach (LLaMEA-SAGE) on the MA-BBOB suite using on the left **gpt-5-nano** vs on the right **gemini-flash-2.0-lite**. Averaged over 5 independent runs.

D Additional Code Evolution Graphs

This appendix provides additional Code Evolution Graphs (CEGs) to complement the analyses presented in Section 5. While the main paper highlights representative runs and selected code features, the figures in this appendix offer a more comprehensive view across benchmarks, runs and structural properties.

First we show CEGs for the SBOX-COST benchmark, including the evolution of features such as mean parameter count, maximum degree and token count over time. Next we report the corresponding graphs for the MA-BBOB benchmark.

Across these figures, node color encodes normalized fitness, while edge color indicates the mutation prompt type and whether code feature guidance requested an increase or decrease of the selected feature (only for LLaMEA-SAGE). Together, these visualizations illustrate how code feature guidance systematically biases structural exploration during the AAD process, while preserving substantial diversity in the generated algorithms.

Fig. 3. Code evolution graph of the max degree code feature of designed algorithms over time for SBOX-COST. Node colour represents normalized fitness where yellow nodes are of high fitness and dark blue nodes of relative low fitness. A yellow edge denotes the use of the **refine prompt**, light blue denotes the use of the **random new prompt**, green denotes an increase of the code feature and the use of the **refine prompt**, dark blue denotes an increase and the use of the **random new prompt**

Fig. 4. Code evolution graph of the mean parameter count code feature of designed algorithms over time for SBOX-COST. Node colour represents normalized fitness where yellow nodes are of high fitness and dark blue nodes of relative low fitness. A yellow edge denotes the use of the **refine prompt**, light blue denotes the use of the **random new prompt**, green denotes an increase of the code feature and the use of the **refine prompt**, dark blue denotes an increase and the use of the **random new prompt**

Fig. 5. Code evolution graph of the mean parameter count code feature of designed algorithms over time for MA-BBOB. Node colour represents normalized fitness where yellow nodes are of high fitness and dark blue nodes of relative low fitness. A yellow edge denotes the use of the **refine prompt**, light blue denotes the use of the **random new prompt**, green denotes an increase of the code feature and the use of the **refine prompt**, dark blue denotes an increase and the use of the **random new prompt**

Fig. 6. Code evolution graph of the total number of code tokens of designed algorithms over time for MA-BBOB. Node colour represents normalized fitness where yellow nodes are of high fitness and dark blue nodes of relative low fitness. A yellow edge denotes the use of the **refine prompt**, light blue denotes the use of the **random new prompt**, green denotes an increase of the code feature and the use of the **refine prompt**, dark blue denotes an increase and the use of the **random new prompt**